

WISELY MANAGED CLASSROOM TECHNOLOGY

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Introduction:

One theme that runs through everything we do is innovation. Sounds like almost everyone else, right? But honestly, it's a word we don't toss around lightly—especially when it comes to education. We believe that finding new and innovative methods of teaching is a crucial skill for teachers.

In the early twentieth century, before the advent of technology in the teaching methods, the instructor was the transmitter and the learners were the receivers of the knowledge being transferred. The typical medium can be imagined as a board, chalk was followed for decades and still in practice at many places. The instructor is the centre of this model delivering factual knowledge to the whole group of learners and having a complete authority in the classroom. The students have a minimum role to play here and the just at the receiving end of the transmission.

Today is the era of science and technology and there is a great need to improve quality of education. The learning mind of students cannot be gauged using conventional methods, rather conventional methods are mostly measuring the memorizing skills of the students instead of bringing clarity to their minds. Brain research has actually shown that certain methods and approaches can truly enhance the learning process, and done right, applying innovative learning and attention-management techniques to classes is a win-win for both students and the teacher.

A teaching method comprises the principles and methods used by teachers to enable student learning. Educationists of today find traditional method of teaching e.g. lecture method, is less effective as the learners may lose their concentration within

half an hour due to passive role and less participation. To overcome this situation there is a need to use innovative teaching strategies. In this research article there are some innovative ideas that will help teachers reinvent their teaching methods.

Wisely managed classroom technology

Computers, tablets, digital cameras, video conferencing technology, and GPS devices can all enhance a student's learning experience. Possible uses of classroom technology include using video games to teach math and foreign languages, Skype to communicate with classrooms or guest speakers from around the world, multimedia projects and software that allow students to explore subject matter using film audio visually.

Let us discuss some methods in detail:

- **Computers in the Classroom:**

Computers have changed the way society functions. Future generations will need to compete with the growing trends of a technologically-driven society that relies on computers to perform daily tasks.

Teachers may encounter students who have already acquired computer skills. In fact, some students may have developed computer proficiency beyond their teachers. This can make it easier for the teacher to incorporate computers into the school curriculum. The majority of public and private schools have already begun the transition to using computers in the classroom. Computers offer teachers the unique ability to collaborate with other educators and professionals opening up worlds of understanding to them and their students. There are many networking sites available to instructors that offer teaching plans and project ideas. Sites like Youtube.com can also prove to be useful when demonstrations or examples are needed to further explain concepts being taught.

Teachers can incorporate several software applications to help students learn more about the course material. Word processors, drill and practice programs, spreadsheet, database programs, and presentation software enable teachers to create fun and interactive ways to help students learn the course material while also reinforcing computer skills. For instance, teachers can direct students to WebQuests.org to

reinforce Internet browsing skills. In addition, it also helps students incorporate research skills to answer homework questions and compose essays. Teachers may also challenge students to create blogs about their coursework for extra credit. Wikis can also help students learn more detailed information about the main points presented in the daily lesson plan.

- **Tablets**

Technology is invading the education field at an increasing pace. The process has effectively evolved from learning on blackboards to learning on interactive whiteboards. Our generation dreamt about using desktop computers to solve math sums, write and draw. The next generation speculated about the benefits of having laptops in the classroom. It's now the era of a tablet, that small immediately operational vehicle of technology and knowledge.

In terms of education, the tablet is a fairly priced, mighty computer that enriches training through the use of an intuitive touch screen and simple controls. The advantages of using electronic devices in learning are common knowledge. An increasing number of traditional classrooms factor in personal-use tablets as part of the curriculum.

As always, some conservative educators are concerned with the tablet being a major distraction. Others argue it's not only a sophisticated toy but a versatile instrument revolutionizing the modern instruction landscape. There is over 15,000 educational apps in Apple's App Store alone, and Google Play is neck and neck. The app ecosystem provides an abundance of learning content for all ages and various knowledge domains.

- **Digital Cameras:**

Digital camera is an electronic device that digitizes images, today you can find one in just about any cell or smart phone. The majority of students today have their own cell or smart phones. One things that we can do to stop them from using phones for degenerative purposes and distractions is, to begin using them as the educational tools that they show so much potential for. Photos may be used in

many different types of classroom lessons. Here are a few application that you and your student's cell or smart phone's digital camera may be used for.

- Use a photo as a prompt for narrative or descriptive writing
- School newspaper, class newspaper or newsletter
- Graphics for written reports and presentations
- e-mail class updates to parents, with attached photos
- Take photos on field trips, to aid in writing about them later
- Publicize a class play or project
- Recording projects and presentations for Open House
- Observe weather over a period of time
- Student portfolio
- Illustrate process for complicated projects
- Illustrate a science experiment

- **Video Conferencing technology**

Talk to and write with a well-known author, visit the zoo and learn about endangered species, travel the deserts, or to an ancient Roman villa and even to China. All from the comfort of your classroom or computer lab. All of this can be accomplished through the power of video conferencing. With the proper equipment and connectivity, students and teachers can take part in video conferencing. Through live video experiences, students are able to gain insight into particular areas of study. They can have real-time, face-to-face interactions with those who know the topic best.

However, introducing new tech devices in the high school classroom often requires that teachers add an element of educational technology leadership to their usual classroom management. Giving students laptops or tablets, for example, means teaching them to use devices respectfully and preventing damage to the equipment. Tech-savvy teachers gave Education Week the following advice on using classroom technology:

- Explain that the use of tech tools in class is a privilege not everyone has—and if abused, it can be discontinued.
- During class, teachers should move around the classroom or use monitoring software to ensure students are using their devices appropriately. When they understand that you will intervene if they go off-task, students know they must focus on their assignment.
- Put students in charge of the upkeep of devices. Classes can learn tech terms, basic maintenance tasks, and appoint a few students to serve as tech monitors responsible for distributing and storing equipment. Doing this creates a sense of value and ownership for the welfare of classroom technology.

These are just few ideas for directions in innovative teaching methods to get students more engaged. In today's increasingly creative world, new ideas are sprung nearly every day. We as teacher should keep learning and keep implementing.

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